

Three classical tests of general relativity from one refractive index

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We observe that the three classical tests of general relativity—gravitational redshift, Shapiro time delay, and light deflection—all follow from a single function: the effective refractive index $n(\rho) = 1 + 2GM/c^2\rho$ that appears in the isotropic Schwarzschild metric at first post-Newtonian order. The metric takes the form $ds^2 = -(2 - n)c^2 dt^2 + n(d\rho^2 + \rho^2 d\Omega^2)$, and the three tests correspond to three operations on n : *evaluating* it at two radii gives the redshift, *integrating* it along a light ray gives the Shapiro delay, and *differentiating* that integral with respect to impact parameter gives the deflection angle. No new physics is introduced; the observation is purely pedagogical.

I. INTRODUCTION

The three classical tests of general relativity—gravitational redshift, the deflection of light by the Sun, and the Shapiro time delay—are usually derived and presented independently. (Historically, the “three classical tests” referred to redshift, light deflection, and Mercury’s perihelion advance; following Shapiro’s 1964 proposal [3], a fourth test was added, and modern usage sometimes groups the three photon tests together. We adopt the latter convention here.) Textbooks introduce the redshift from the time-time component of the metric, the deflection from the geodesic equation or from a variational principle, and the Shapiro delay from the coordinate speed of light integrated along the ray path.

In this note we observe that all three derivations reduce to operations on a single scalar field: the effective refractive index $n(\rho)$ of the Schwarzschild gravitational field in isotropic coordinates. The first post-Newtonian (1PN) metric has a particularly clean structure in terms of n , and the three tests emerge as three natural operations on this one function:

- *evaluate* n at two radii \rightarrow gravitational redshift,
- *integrate* n along a light ray \rightarrow Shapiro delay,
- *differentiate* that integral with respect to impact parameter \rightarrow light deflection.

The identification is not new in pieces—the optical-mechanical analogy for light propagation in a gravitational field goes back at least to Einstein [1] and was formalized by Gordon [2]—but presenting the three tests as three operations on one function makes the common structure explicit.

II. THE $(2 - n, n)$ METRIC

In isotropic coordinates (ρ, θ, ϕ) , the Schwarzschild metric at 1PN order reads

$$ds^2 = -\left(1 - \frac{2m}{\rho}\right)c^2 dt^2 + \left(1 + \frac{2m}{\rho}\right)(d\rho^2 + \rho^2 d\Omega^2), \quad (1)$$

where $m \equiv GM/c^2$ is the gravitational radius and $d\Omega^2 = d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2$. This is the standard weak-field expansion of the exact isotropic Schwarzschild solution, accurate through order m/ρ .

Define the *refractive index field*

$$n(\rho) \equiv 1 + \frac{2m}{\rho}. \quad (2)$$

The spatial part of the metric (1) is $n\delta_{ij}$ in Cartesian isotropic coordinates, while the time-time component satisfies $|g_{00}| = 1 - 2m/\rho = 2 - n$. (Here n is a coordinate-dependent 1PN optical analogue in isotropic coordinates, not a material refractive index.) The full metric is therefore

$$ds^2 = -(2 - n)c^2 dt^2 + n(d\rho^2 + \rho^2 d\Omega^2). \quad (3)$$

The entire 1PN gravitational field of a spherical mass is encoded in one function $n(\rho)$. We now show that each classical test is a different reading of this function.

III. GRAVITATIONAL REDSHIFT: EVALUATE

A photon emitted at radius ρ_1 and received at ρ_2 in a static field experiences a frequency ratio

$$\frac{\nu_2}{\nu_1} = \frac{\sqrt{|g_{00}(\rho_1)|}}{\sqrt{|g_{00}(\rho_2)|}} = \sqrt{\frac{2 - n(\rho_1)}{2 - n(\rho_2)}}. \quad (4)$$

Since $n - 1 \ll 1$, expanding to leading order gives

$$\frac{\nu_2}{\nu_1} \approx 1 + \frac{n(\rho_1) - n(\rho_2)}{2}. \quad (5)$$

For a photon climbing out of a gravitational well ($\rho_1 < \rho_2$, so $n_1 > n_2$), the received frequency is lower: the photon is redshifted. The fractional shift is

$$z = \frac{n_1 - n_2}{2} = m\left(\frac{1}{\rho_1} - \frac{1}{\rho_2}\right) = \frac{GM}{c^2}\left(\frac{1}{\rho_1} - \frac{1}{\rho_2}\right), \quad (6)$$

the standard result. The redshift is obtained by *evaluating* n at two points and taking the difference.

IV. SHAPIRO DELAY: INTEGRATE

For a null ray, $ds^2 = 0$ in Eq. (3) gives

$$(2 - n) c^2 dt^2 = n dl^2, \quad (7)$$

where $dl^2 = d\rho^2 + \rho^2 d\Omega^2$ is the isotropic spatial line element. The coordinate speed of light is

$$\frac{dl}{dt} = c \sqrt{\frac{2-n}{n}} \approx c(1 - 2m/\rho), \quad (8)$$

so the effective refractive index governing the coordinate travel time is

$$n_{\text{eff}} = \frac{c}{dl/dt} = \sqrt{\frac{n}{2-n}} \approx n, \quad (9)$$

to first post-Newtonian order. (Writing $\epsilon = 2m/\rho$, we have $\sqrt{(1+\epsilon)/(1-\epsilon)} = 1 + \epsilon + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2) = n + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$, confirming the approximation.)

The coordinate time for light to travel between two points is therefore

$$cT = \int n dl. \quad (10)$$

The time *excess* over flat-space propagation is

$$c \Delta T = \int (n - 1) dl = 2m \int \frac{dl}{\rho}. \quad (11)$$

For a ray traveling from ρ_1 to ρ_2 at closest approach b to the central mass, evaluating the integral along the unperturbed straight-line path gives [3, 4]

$$\Delta T = \frac{2GM}{c^3} \ln \frac{4\rho_1\rho_2}{b^2}, \quad (12)$$

in the limit $\rho_1, \rho_2 \gg b$. The Shapiro delay is obtained by *integrating* $(n - 1)$ along the light path.

V. LIGHT DEFLECTION: DIFFERENTIATE

By Fermat's principle, a light ray in a static spacetime follows the path that extremizes the optical path length $S = \int n dl$. For a ray with impact parameter b , the deflection angle can be obtained from [5]

$$\delta = -\frac{\partial}{\partial b} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (n - 1) dl, \quad (13)$$

evaluated along the unperturbed straight-line path at distance b from the center.

Using coordinates where the ray travels along the l -axis at perpendicular distance b , so that $\rho = \sqrt{b^2 + l^2}$, we have $n - 1 = 2m/\sqrt{b^2 + l^2}$. Then

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (n - 1) dl = 2m \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{dl}{\sqrt{b^2 + l^2}} = 2m \left[\ln(l + \sqrt{l^2 + b^2}) \right]_{-\infty}^{+\infty}. \quad (14)$$

This integral diverges logarithmically, but its derivative with respect to b does not. Equivalently, one may compute the deflection directly as

$$\delta = -\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\partial n}{\partial b} dl = 2m \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{b}{(b^2 + l^2)^{3/2}} dl. \quad (15)$$

Evaluating the standard integral,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{dl}{(b^2 + l^2)^{3/2}} = \frac{2}{b^2}, \quad (16)$$

gives

$$\delta = \frac{4m}{b} = \frac{4GM}{c^2 b}, \quad (17)$$

the Einstein deflection. The bending angle is obtained by *differentiating* the optical path integral with respect to impact parameter.

VI. SUMMARY

TABLE I. Three classical tests as operations on the refractive index $n(\rho) = 1 + 2GM/c^2\rho$.

Test	Operation on n	Result
Redshift	evaluate: $\frac{n_1 - n_2}{2}$	$\frac{GM}{c^2} \left(\frac{1}{\rho_1} - \frac{1}{\rho_2} \right)$
Shapiro delay	integrate: $\frac{1}{c} \int (n - 1) dl$	$\frac{2GM}{c^3} \ln \frac{4\rho_1\rho_2}{b^2}$
Deflection	differentiate: $-\frac{\partial}{\partial b} \int (n - 1) dl$	$\frac{4GM}{c^2 b}$

Table I collects the results. The 1PN Schwarzschild metric in isotropic coordinates is determined by one scalar field $n(\rho)$ through the $(2 - n, n)$ structure of Eq. (3), and the three classical tests of general relativity correspond to three operations on n : evaluate it at two radii, integrate it along a light ray, or differentiate that integral with respect to impact parameter.

This perspective may be useful in teaching. Rather than presenting the three tests as separate calculations requiring separate machinery, an instructor could introduce $n(\rho)$ once and derive all three as corollaries. The refractive-index viewpoint also makes the results physically intuitive: photons propagate more slowly (in coordinate time) where gravity is stronger, and every observable consequence of this slowdown follows from the spatial profile of n .

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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- [1] A. Einstein, “On the influence of gravitation on the propagation of light,” *Ann. Phys. (Leipzig)* **35**, 898–908 (1911).
- [2] W. Gordon, “Zur Lichtfortpflanzung nach der Relativitätstheorie,” *Ann. Phys. (Leipzig)* **72**, 421–456 (1923).
- [3] I. I. Shapiro, “Fourth test of general relativity,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **13**, 789–791 (1964).
- [4] C. M. Will, “The confrontation between general relativity and experiment,” *Living Rev. Relativ.* **17**, 4 (2014).
- [5] S. Weinberg, *Gravitation and Cosmology* (Wiley, New York, 1972), Sec. 8.5.